

HyFL: A Hybrid Framework For Private Federated Learning (Supplementary Material)

This document provides additional evaluation results of our HyFL framework.

Fig. 1. Validation accuracy for ResNet9/CIFAR10 training with FedAvg, FLTrust, and trimmed mean for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the cluster-focused setting.

Fig. 2. Validation accuracy for LeNet/MNIST training with FedAvg, FLTrust, and trimmed mean for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the equally-distributed setting.

Fig. 3. Validation accuracy for LeNet/MNIST training with FedAvg, FLTrust, and trimmed mean for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the focused setting.

Fig. 4. Validation accuracy for LeNet/MNIST training with FedAvg, FLTrust, and trimmed mean for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the cluster-focused setting.

Fig. 5. Validation accuracy for ResNet9/CIFAR10 training with trimmed mean and our trimmed mean variant for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the equally-distributed setting.

Fig. 6. Validation accuracy for ResNet9/CIFAR10 training with trimmed mean and our trimmed mean variant for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the focused setting.

Fig. 7. Validation accuracy for ResNet9/CIFAR10 training with trimmed mean and our trimmed mean variant for 2000 iterations under RLF, SLF, DLF, and TLF attacks in the cluster-focused setting.